

NAME: Nakkara

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SOURCE(S): Eather, Bronwyn, *A grammar of Nakkara (Central Arnhem Land Coast)*, PL 7101 EAT 1990

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Revised Word Questionnaire (Oct 2003)

PHONETIC & PHONOLOGICAL QUESTIONS

• Note also that a form may be phonologically "free" or independent, while not necessarily constituting a lexical category (i.e. "noun" or "verb" or "adjective"). I am especially interested in grammatical forms that are phonologically independent (and also lexical forms that are phonologically dependent upon something else—cannot occur alone phonologically, but they express a meaning that you might otherwise think of as "word")

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

--occurrence of segments, limitations, prohibitions

--voicing, aspiration patterns

--place (either specific like bilabial, lamino-dental, or general like anterior, coronal, etc.)

--manner patterns (plosive, affricate, fricative, tap, approx, etc.)

p. 24 no stops clusters in word initial position

-- gemination / long stops

p. 20-21: word-initial stops are always short and word-final stops are always long

The author insists on the distinction between a geminate clusters and long stop allophones (on the basis of phoneme economy and because of the distributional parallel between stop clusters and long stops)

*A true **geminate** cluster occurs only in morpheme-medial position, it is not predictable:*

*'bu**d**a – 'to hit, kill' 'bu**d**:a – 'yabby' (**d**/**d**: - apico-post-alveolar stop)*

*A **long stop allophones** occur in a number of environments:*

- *in syllable final position (and consequently in word final position). Short stops, on the contrary occur only in syllable-(and word-) initial positions.*

- *root-initial stops in word-medial post-vocalic position is always long ('stop alternation')*:

p. 29 Ex. Root 'gaɾama 'get up' :

nurba-	'g:ɑɾama-	da
2AUG(S)-	get.up-	PC/T
'you lot got up'		

∅-	'g:ɑɾama-	da
3M(S)-	get.up-	PC/T
'he got up'		

- *stop-initial nominal suffix always has a long stop and never alternates (p. 32*

Allophonic lengthening of morpheme-initial stops is triggered by the morpheme boundary of

nominal stem and suffix). Verbal suffixes behave differently (not explained on p. 32)

- vowel height/backness (quality)
- nasal vowels (see "rules")
- vowel length
- VV sequences (includes diphthongs)
- idiosyncratic, segment-specific restrictions or possibilities, like "no labiodental approximants at starting edge, even though they occur medially etc."

2. "Rules" Part 1

Some phonological processes are restricted in application to the internal domain of a phonologically independent unit, and others are restricted to the boundaries/edges. Sometimes these differences are explicitly noted, others may be implicit. Please list the major processes that highlight such boundaries. Do these things happen to lexical forms only, to grammatical forms only, or to both?

Note types and locations of:

- vowel/consonant HARMONY/assimilation/dissimilation (note the types—place, manner, voicing, other)

1) **p. 46 Stop alternation:** *'a word-medial stop lengthens where it is postvocalic and is the 1st consonant of a root, or where it is the 1st consonant of a nominal suffix; in either case a syllable final stop is created, identical to the root- or suffix-initial stop.'*

$\emptyset > [C_{i-sonorant}] / V _ [C_{i-sonorant} \text{ ROOT}]$

$\emptyset > [C_{i-sonorant}] / _ [C_{i-sonorant} \text{ NOM.SUFFIX}]$

p. 29 In verbs and nominals:

p. 29 Ex. Root 'garama 'get up' :

<i>nurba-</i>	<i>'g:arɛama-</i>	<i>da</i>
<i>2AUG(S)-</i>	<i>get.up-</i>	<i>PC/T</i>
<i>'you lot got up'</i>		

$\emptyset-$	<i>'g:arɛama-</i>	<i>da</i>
<i>3M(S)-</i>	<i>get.up-</i>	<i>PC/T</i>
<i>'he got up'</i>		

p. 30 In reduplication of type A. The whole reduplicated section is treated as the root and stop length occurs only where the first occurrence of the reduplicated morpheme is word-medial and post vocalic:

'gara- gara- wab:a - 'all long'
na- 'g:ara- gara - 'long way'

p. 33 In reduplication of type B: only the second occurrence of the reduplicated morpheme shows the stop length (and that's why 'can be compared with nominal suffix components')

bi'ri- b:iri - 'fighting stick'

In compounds (see under compounds)

Nominal suffixes:

/na-gaḍa-ŋa-ba-gawa/ > nag:aḍanab:ag:awa 'from there'

2) Apical Neutralisation Rule

/ḍ/, /ŋ/, /l/ > [d], [n], [l] word-initially and after [m], [n], [ŋ]

/Ø-ḍawa-ḍa/ > dawada 's/he threw it away'

/gara-ḍam-ḍam/ > garaḍamdām/ 'chin'

3) Nasal-laminal stop assimilation

An alveolar nasal assimilates to the place of articulation of a following laminal stop. Although the process of assimilation can happen

/ya-n-ʒoŋa/ > /ya-ŋ-ʒoŋa/ 'he will come back'

--segment DELETION/epenthesis, any kind of insertion/deletion processes

--segment METATHESIS or any type of re-ordering

3. "Rules" Part 2

Some rules referring to possible (and prohibited) syllable structures, processes of syllabification, and also to suprasegmental processes are sensitive to the domain of a phonologically independent unit. The distribution of these processes may help to define the boundaries and internal composition of such units.

Note:

--**THE DEFAULT syllable template**, and whether or not this template applies to the edges of phonologically free units. For example, a language may allow C clusters in coda position, but this may only happen at the ending edge of a phon. free unit, and not internally (or the other way around)

Canonical syllable types :

C - syllabic nasals /ŋ/, /ŋ/ and an isolated example of /ŋ/ and syllabic rhotic /r/ Always in word initial position, are often prefix morphemes and do not carry primary stress.

Ex. ʀ.bag.ga.ḍa.bi.ya.na – 'they'll go down'

p. 65 'There is no straightforward way of providing their status as syllabic consonants, as

against, say, the 1st segment of a consonant cluster. The fact is that my perception of them has always been that of syllabic; the perceived duration of these consonants is sufficient for them to be counted as individual syllables. '

C₁V(C₂) – this syllable type can occur in any part of a word,

Restrictions:

C₁-position

- in word final position no /n/ or /ŋ/ in CVC syllables
- in word-initial position their inventory is restricted by apical neutralization (retroflex/apico-post-alveolar stop, nasals and laterals are excluded).

C₂ position

- no /w/ or /r/ in C₂ position word medially
- no /b/, /w/, /r/, /r/ and /y/ (so no rhotics and no semivowels) in C₂ position word finally

C₁VC₂C₃

- C₂ can only be a rhotic or a lateral or /y/ (but no /y/ in the word final syllable)
- C₃ is always a stop: word-initially and –medially any stop except /d/, word-finally – only /g/ is allowed

baɖ.ɟelg.baɖ.ɟelg – ‘Brown Goshawk’

--**SUPER heavy** syllables (Hall 2001). Can something that is phonologically free end with a super-heavy syllable?

Yes, see above, CVCC syllables word-finally with rhotic/lateral + /g/

--STRESS

--is there a primary stress rule? what is the domain?

p. 35 Primary stress is assigned to the 1st vowel of the root morpheme it is accompanied by vowel lengthening. Secondary stress normally falls on the penultimate syllable and then on alternating syllables preceding the penultimate (i. e. in a right-to-left direction), but doesn't occur on the syllable immediately following the one that is assigned primary stress. In

compounds each root is assigned stress on the 1st syllable, but just one of the roots bears prominent primary stress.

Ex.: gabar-na-marba:-wab:aŋ-eba > ,gabarna'marba:,wab:a,ŋeba (, = secondary stress)

--what types of forms are included, what is exempted?

--what are the minimal/maximal domains for stress to apply? Can a phonologically free unit that is simply (C)V take the main stress?

--can only lexical forms take a main stress, or can independent grammatical forms also take it?

4. Minimality & Maximality

Look at the grammar, look also at the dictionary/glossary entries if they are included. What is the most common (or only) minimal and maximal size of a phon. free unit?

Though disyllabic phonologically free units are not so seldom, the language seem to prefer units of 4-7 syllables.

Or alternatively, what is the minimal/maximal morphological complexity/composition of something that is phonologically free? (C)V? CV (with an initial crucially present)? di- or polysyllable?

The smallest unit I found was a disyllabic word.

How big can a free unit be in terms of syllable number?

p. 35: up to 13 syllables

Do these size constraints apply only to lexical forms? If there are constraints, must a lexical form be bimorphemic to be free? If so, what morphemes qualify? Any & all?

5. Reduplication

Is the entire unit copied? More? Less? Can something of any phonological size/complexity have reduplication (even if the process is semantically restricted)? If there are different *types* of reduplication, see if you can find patterns, or note what the author says.

Is the resulting suprasegmental pattern of a reduplicated form the same or different from a single free form? (Are there 2 main stresses or 1? 2 tones? a different tone altogether?)

Reduplication is not a productive process of word-formation in Nakkara (57 words)

There are 2 types of reduplication:

Type A reduplications are treated as having a single root morpheme boundary rather than 2 or more, stop length occurs in line with the rules formulated above: stop length occurs only where the first occurrence of the reduplicated morpheme is word-medial and post vocalic:

'gara- gara- wab:a - 'all long'

na- 'g:ara- gara - 'long way'

Type B reduplications – only the second occurrence of the reduplicated morpheme shows the stop length (the way it happens with nominal suffixes).

There are two subtypes of the type B:

With irregular stress:

/bora + bora/ > bo'rab:ora 'Brush Turkey'

/gala + gala/ > ga'lag:ala 'chicken'

With regular stress (major stress on the first part, secondary stress on the second):

/gana + gana/ > 'gana,g:ana 'always'

7. Phonological Units in Morphologically Complex Forms

--COMPOUNDING: note any patterns of segmental alteration with compounds—especially at the edges of compounds; note prior and resulting stress/tone patterns; note segmental restrictions in compounds

p. 34: 'Stress patterning generally determines whether a component root morpheme in a compound is treated as a word root or as a suffix, but in either case stop lengthening occurs precisely where the generalization would predict. Compound-internal prefixes never have morpheme-initial stop length, but in all cases except one, a root-morpheme-initial stop will be long if that morpheme receives primary word stress, or follows such a morpheme, as suffixes generally do.'

/wu- na- 'gaɖja- 'guɾbara/ > wuna'g:adɟag:uɾbara 'sorcerer'

(I think, the second g: exemplifies these roots treated as suffixes, where we have stop lengthening in the morpheme following the stressed morpheme.)'

--"SIMPLE juxtaposition or concatenation of 2+ independent forms"—these are things that might be called "serialization" in some grammars: note any phonological discussion of these things. single tone? single stress? segment changes? ordering restrictions? co-occurrence restrictions?

--MULTI-morphemic forms: this is already discussed in above sections, but note especially phonologically free units that are minimally bimorphemic (or bigger), note any allomorphy that suggests that multi-morphemic forms behave as a single phonological unit.

--IF a language has a wide variety of inflectional affixes, do all stem-affix combinations have the same/similar stress, syllabification, segmental patterns, phon rules, tones, etc? Describe those that deviate from the set "general" patterns. Give examples. In German, for example, a stem + certain suffixes behaves as a **single** phonological unit ([li:**bx**] 'love 1.sg'), but a stem + certain other suffixes behaves as **2** phonological units ([li:**p**.liç] 'dearly')—the resyllabification & voicing of the plosive is evidence of this.

Be sensitive to exceptions/variations in segmental/phonotactic, prosodic rules that may suggest that certain things "go together" phonologically, and others that do not. Explicitly state the conditions under which variations apply.